

EXPLORING THE PRINCIPALS' QUALITY CONTROL APPROACHES AND TEACHERS' TASK PERFORMANCE IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN UYO, AKWA IBOM STATE

BY

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Abstract

Secondary schools in Nigeria have gone through rapid transformation. However, there are still areas that need urgent surgical operation such as the sustainability of its quality. Principals who are the engine room at ensuring that quality in secondary schools is sustained, employed various quality control mechanisms on teachers in performing its role. Considering the above, the study explores principals' quality control approaches and teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. Three research questions were raised to guide the study. The descriptive design was used, more so, the population of the study is 2078, and simple random sampling technique was used to select 573 participants for the study. Two instruments were used to gather data from the participants. The instruments validated and their reliability was 0.81. The instruments faced validation and cronbach alpha reliability were 0.81. Simple linear regression was used to analyse the data. The findings established among others that effective supervision of teachers by the principals enhances their task performance which eventually increases the overall productivity. Considering the above findings, it is recommended that Principals should take up refresher courses on human resources management, because most of them have poor human relation with their teachers, therefore, when this happened, teachers distance themselves from them prompting the total collapse education system.

Keywords: Principals, quality control, teachers, task performance

Introduction

Education is one of the sectors in Nigeria which touches every aspect of human endeavour. In fact, the relevance of education cannot be measured based on its socioeconomic emancipation of the individual and the nation. Moreover, education plays an important role in bringing about changes in society. Gana (2020) sees education as a vehicle for individual and national development. Considering the above assertion, Nigeria as a developing nation tries to educate her young population. In fact, current and successive government in Nigeria has spent billions of Naira at ensuring that the citizens are educated. This is through the provision of teaching and learning facilities in schools. In secondary schools which the study focuses on, a lot has happened in the past, and it is currently happening in this sector. For instance, some

principals who are the managers of these schools exhibit complete neglect towards their duties. Furthermore, some teachers on the other hand failed in their responsibility of teaching the children.

The primary aim of secondary education is to ensure acquisition of knowledge and production of graduates who are prepared for higher education (National Policy on Education, 2013). Similarly, Onuma (2017) argued that secondary education prepares people for becoming useful members of society with intellectual competences to help in the growth and development of the nation. However, the accomplishment of these laudable educational objectives depends on various quality control measures adopted by principals in ensuring effective school administration (Ohamobi & Anasiudu, 2024). For the sake of this study, quality control is an effective coordination and

control of teaching and learning activities by the school principals (Chinwem & Ugba, 2025). Based on the above, principals adopt different quality control measures in ensuring that teachers carry out their teaching duties. Furthermore, principals' quality control measures consist of effective and efficient management of resources (Ayeni, 2020), which produce quality output that meets the expectations of the society (Ayeni & Afolabi, 2012). Okoye, Onyali and Ezeugbor (2016) argued that to ensure quality control in schools, it is necessary to have competent and effective principals and teachers.

In recent times, most Nigerians has been glamouring for a complete review of secondary school curriculum due to the 'perceived' failing of education. Most graduates from our secondary schools hardly perform simple task, therefore putting the quality of the products to question. Ibrahim, Arshad and Salleh (2017) were of the view that the quality of our secondary schools is nothing to write home about due to the inability of its products engaging in any meaningful academic exercise in the society. The question in the mind of most scholars and researchers is that, would the review of secondary education curriculum bring about the desire to achieve a high academic standard? Ademola, Okebukola, Oladejo, Onowugbeda, Gbeleyi and Agbanimu (2021) argued that the review of school curriculum alone does not guarantee high standard of education in the country, rather, principals' quality control measure, teachers' qualification and competency and provision of instructional resources play significant role in this direction. Considering the above discussion, it is irresistible to submit that the principal's main function is to maintain high quality control measures in our secondary schools in accordance with the laid down regulations by the ministry. However, the issue of whether principals exercise the role of ensuring quality control measures is debatable and the future research

topic. Here, the paper explores the principals' quality control approaches and teachers' task performance in secondary schools in Uyo, Nigeria. Considering the above topic and discussion, the study is guided by the following objectives as stated below;

1. To examine ways principals' instructional supervision impact teachers' task performance in secondary schools
2. To examine ways principals' disciplinary approach influence teachers' task performance secondary schools
3. To determine principals' school facilities maintenance, impact teachers' task performance in secondary schools

Research Questions

Based on the objective, the following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. How do principals' instructional supervision impact teachers' task performance in secondary schools?
2. How do principals' disciplinary measures influence teachers' task performance in secondary schools?
3. How do principals' school facilities maintenance impact teachers' task performance in schools?

Theoretical framework

The theory that underpins the study is known as Human Relation Theory (HRT) by Elton Mayo. HRT is a management measure that emphasizes the importance of employee satisfaction, morale, and other social factors is out to achieve organisational goals. This theory opined that by improving social bonds, working conditions, and employee treatment, business can increase productivity, and motivation would be achieved by staffers. In fact, human relations entail the ability to communicate freely, provide incentives to staff, be open, honest and kind with all the staff in the organization. The implications of this theory to educational administration are that it

steers managerial focus towards an emphasis on employee enthusiasm, morale and contentment rather than just productivity alone. In addition, “a school in which a principal utilizes a human relations perspective is one in which the staff feel they are able to work freely as a team without coercion or manipulation from administration” (Thamarasseri, 2016). The above theory is relevance in the study to tease out ways principals’ quality control approaches impact teachers’ task performance in secondary schools.

Literature

The importance of quality control in any establishment cannot be ignored as it is the only measure through which customer satisfaction can be guaranteed and enhanced profit. Quality Control deals with the effective coordination and control of teaching and learning activities by principals. It involves efficient management, monitoring, evaluation and review of resources input and transformation process (teaching and learning) to produce quality output that meets the standard and expectation of the society (Ayeni & Afolabi, 2012). This implies that quality control involves putting different mechanisms and measures in place to ensure that the ultimate goals of education are achieved. In an educational institution for instance, Ebuara (2012) notes that poor quality control measures would certainly lead to poor quality output of graduates for the sector.

In another vein, discipline is very vital in any educational institution to achieve the goals of education. Teachers require discipline to instill discipline in others. Aguba (2009) states that discipline means self-control, control of conduct including habits, action, desires, emotions, impulses and general behaviour. Akpan (2013) posited that discipline is the acceptance of rules and regulations with the aim of achieving specific goals. In the school setting, discipline is highly essential if the educational aims are to be achieved. The classroom teacher requires

discipline before she/he can instill discipline in others. Principal that implements effective discipline propagates a cooperative learning environment for teachers to carry out their duties effectively and efficiently (Ogbo, Anyanwu, Emengini, Okeke-James & Umeozor, 2021). Ramli, Mundzir, Suprianto, Ashadi and Arifudin (2024) opined that discipline is essential because staff cannot work successfully, without establishing standards of behaviour (discipline) for the attainment of institutional goals and objectives.

In another circumstance, studies such as Erdoğan, Haktanır, Kuru, Parpucu and Tüylü (2022); Handrianto, Jusoh, Syuraini, Rouzi and Alghazo (2022) argued that mentorship is a form of quality control approach because it stressed the importance of positive reinforcement on behavioural change. Dunlami and Anyanwu (2024) argued that when appropriate monitorship is put in place in the system, it helps to checkmates and ensure that requisite data for judging quality is obtained. It is obvious to say that the quality assurance in schools involve all the attitudes, objectives, actions and procedures that through their application and usage will savage unnecessary wastage and fruitless effort. The issue of teachers’ job performance in the school is critical because of its importance development of both the students and school. In this paper, teachers’ job performance is regarded as the duties performed by a teacher at a particular period in the school system in achieving organisational goals. Additionally, Werang (2019) argued that it is the ability of teachers to combine relevant inputs for the enhancement of teaching and learning processes. However, it was submitted that teacher job performance is determined by the level of participation in the day-to-day running of the organization (Li, Kanchanapoom, Deeprasert, Duan & Qi, 2025). It could also be described as the ability of teachers to combine relevant inputs for the enhancement of teaching and learning

processes (Olaifa, Odumosu, Alao, Ibrahim & Sagaya, 2025). Supporting this argument, Chinenye, Ughamadu and Maduili (2025) asserted that variables of job performance such as effective teaching, lesson note preparation, effective use of scheme of work, effective supervision, monitoring of students' work and disciplinary ability are virtues which teachers should uphold effectively in the school system. In this regard, one may argue that teachers' performance would be a function of principal's quality assurance control on teaching, lesson preparation, lesson presentation, mastery of subject matter, competence, teachers' commitment to job and extra-curricular activities.

Methodology

This study adopted descriptive research design. This design was adopted because it identifies the patterns in which the data answer questions of who, what, where, when, and to what extent. Based on the above notion, the study sought the relationship between the independent variable

(principals' quality control measures) and the dependent variable (teachers' task performance). In another vein, the population of the study are 300 principals and 2078 teachers in secondary schools in Uyo, Nigeria. In summary, a total of 2378 constitutes the population of the study (Ministry of Education, 2025). Furthermore, the researcher adopted simple random sampling technique to select one hundred and ninety-one (191) principals and three hundred and eighty-two (382) teachers from twenty (20) secondary schools in the Metropolis. Similarly, research instruments used were Principals Quality Control Measures Questionnaire (PQCMQ) and Teachers Task Performance Questionnaire (TTPQ) for teachers and principals respectively. Face and content validity was done. Additionally, reliability of the instrument was established at the coefficient of 0.81. All ethical issues were strictly adhered to. The study employed simple linear regression statistical tool to answer the questions.

Results

Research Question1: How do principals' instructional supervision impact teachers' task performance in secondary schools?

Table 1: Simple Linear Regression for Principals' Instructional Supervision and Teachers' Task Performance

Variable	Sum of squares	of R	R-square	Extent of contribution	Remark
Instructional Supervision	236.80	.212	.045	4.5%	Low extent of prediction
Teachers' task performance	5008.02				

The R-Value of .212 indicated low extent of prediction between the two variables. The calculated R² of .045 which is the coefficient of determinant, indicated that only 4.5% of teachers' tasks performance is predicted by

principals' instructional supervision. This implied that the principals' instructional supervision indicating low extent significantly predicts high teachers' tasks performance in the class.

Research Question 2: How do principals’ disciplinary measures predict teachers’ task performance?

Table 2: Simple Linear Regression for Principals’ Disciplinary Measures and Teachers’ Task Performance

Variable	Sum of squares	R	R-square	Extent of contribution	Remark
Principals’ disciplinary approach	173.28	.82	.033	3.3%	Very low extent of prediction
Teachers’ task performance	5071.53				

The R-values of .82 have shown that there was low extent of prediction between the two variables which is principal disciplinary approach and teachers task performance. The calculated R² of .033 which is the coefficient of determination indicated that only 3.3% of

teachers’ task performance is predicted by principals’ disciplinary measures. It implied that principals’ disciplinary approach which is low positively predicted teachers’ task performance in the class.

Research Question 3: How does principals’ school facilities maintenance impact teachers’ task performance?

Table 3: Simple Linear Regression for Principals’ School facilities maintenance and Teachers’ Task Performance

Variable	Sum of squares	R	R-square	Extent of contribution	Remark
Principals’ School Facility Maintenance	112.07	.146	.021	2.1%	Low extent of prediction
Teachers’ task performance	5132.74				

Table 3 showed the R value for the strength of prediction and R² for the determination of the extent of prediction between principal school facilities maintenance and teachers tasks performance. Similarly, the R-Value of .146 indicated low extent of prediction between the two variables earlier mentioned. Moreover, the calculated R² of .021 which is the coefficient of determination indicated that 2.1% of teachers’ task performance is predicted by principal facilities maintenance, which invariably means that the principal facilities maintenance significantly enhances teachers’ task performance.

classroom. In fact, this means that effective supervision of teachers by the principals enhances their task performance, which eventually increases the overall productivity in school environment. In other words, anytime a principal visits the classroom and he /she checks teachers’ lesson plan, ensure the availability and utilization of instructional materials, mark class teachers’ register regularly, and keep closer watch on teacher religiously, there is a possibility for the teacher to improve his/her overall task performance in the class. This will eventually impact students’ academic performance. The findings of this study agree with the position held by Sule, Ameh and Egbai (2015) who argued that there is a strong relationship between principals’ instructional supervisory practices and enhancement of teachers’ productivity in the class.

Discussion of Findings

Findings indicated that there is a significant relationship between principals’ instructional supervision and teachers’ task performance in

From the analysis, the findings indicated that principals' disciplinary approach positively promotes teachers' overall performance in the class. In other words, if the principal check teachers' lesson plan periodically, and equally set rules and regulations for staff to follow, therefore, any teacher who failed in this direction is sanctioned. This serves as a deterrence for other teachers who plan to take his or her official duties with levity. In fact, the principal disciplinary measure promotes teachers' official responsibility in the class which is beneficial to students' academic output. Owan and Ekpe (2019) had earlier said that there is moderate positive relationship which is statistically significant between suspension and teachers' job effectiveness in public primary schools. Furthermore, where there is effectiveness in the dismissal (disciplinary measure) of teachers, it will certainly lead to an improvement in the quality of teachers' job effectiveness and vice versa (Apalia, 2017).

Finding from the question established that the principal facilities maintenance significantly enhances teachers' task performance. Effective maintenance of school facilities by the principals significantly helps in enhancing effective teaching, therefore, improve teachers' task performance which leads to the attainment of the institution's goals and objectives. In fact, this position agrees with Njoroge and Sisa's (2023) position who said that there is a significant correlation between students' academic performance and the facilities availability and maintenance by the principal in secondary schools in the Bungoma South sub-county. Similarly, Nwile and Inukan-Adebayo (2022) held that the dilapidated structures in schools and its poor maintenance positively affect the teaching and learning in public senior secondary schools.

Conclusion

It was concluded based on the findings that, the extent to which principals' quality control measures relate to teachers' task performance is significant in secondary Schools in Uyo. Principals are internal supervisors that oversee all the activities within the school and ensure that both teachers and students are well behaved and carry out their assigned tasks effectively for the attainment of predetermined goals and objectives. Principals that effectively supervise instruction, maintain high disciplinary standards, maintain a good school facilities maintenance culture, and mentoring of teachers in their schools would get teachers perform their tasks effectively in secondary schools.

Recommendations

From the findings, the following recommendations were reached;

- a). Principals should take refresher courses on human resources management, because most of them has poor human relation with their teachers, therefore, when this happened, teachers distance themselves from them prompting the total collapse education system.
- b). Government should provide funds to principal to carry out maintenance of facilities in the school to enhance effective teaching and learning.

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